

Strengthening Competitiveness Education and Technology in Regions of Indonesia

Khalsiah, Faculty of Education and Teacher Training, Universitas Malikusaleh Aceh, Indonesia.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7299213

Abstract

Epistemologically the quality of technology-based education will be able to adapt to changing times. Education and Technology, which products continuously experience a cycle of development and change that is very fast, and humans are required to adjust to technological capabilities. The advancement of education and technology has revolutionized and produced significant findings. Consequently, it is critical to consider how education and technology will be able to control human society today. The quality of cultured education with character will be shaped by education and the development of the nation's culture. Quality and a technology-based education system that will improve academic abilities, create ideal research, and develop innovations and various states of arts in education characterize the dynamics produced in science. It is frequently unclear whether the ability of technology and human civilization will be the same as the world of education.

Keywords: Strength, Competitiveness, Education, Technology, Regions, Indonesia.

Introduction

The boost technology-based education has a powerful influence. It dominates not only in developing countries, and the impact of technological media is also monopolized by developed countries where the technology and education sectors are booming - both in the public sector and the business-industrial sector. Developed countries face similar issues, which have a long and intense historical interaction with education. Conceptually, technology is analogized to penetrate the worlds of theory and practice, development, management, and utilization as a source of learning in education. It naturally depicts a portrait of civilizations' progress in a vision of the development of educational technology in various regions of Indonesia.

Media in a democratic system, using the technology of philosopher Juergen Habermas, should function as a public space arena. What is meant by public space is a place where all members of society can interact, exchange ideas, and general debate issues without fear of economic authorities intervening (Sudiby, 2004:70). Harjanto (1997: 245) discusses how educational technology will influence a simple message theory so that it does not verbalise the need for space, time, and sense limitations and the use of appropriate and diverse technology or media to create the same perception of a problem The public sphere creates the potential for democracy.

The problem is that educational media is not a vacuum at all. Educational media is an

arena of contestation against interests trying to seize the science and technology space, to hegemonies the public. There is interplay between the structure and the agent in social space construction. The phenomenon of technology-based educational media when dealing with the political power of the state and the power of the market economy. The media is controlled by state regulation, the media fail to create public space. State regulation defines the information framework in a frame legitimized by the state.

The same thing happens when the power of the capitalist economy controls the media. The influence of technology in education is a breakthrough that is very close to the ease of access to hardware and software as a medium for developing learning technology for therapy, but it also has an impact on research and management and has an effect on learning media in a country. The definition of educational technology emphasizes learning through applicative learning through media which results in communication media through learning from traditional teaching materials to form television, film, OHP and other software media technologies. Systematically, learning technology was born due to systematically evaluating the overall combination of effective educational processes.

Literature Review

The definition of education (2004) defines it as a practical study of the learning process through appropriate technological processes. BarbaraB. See's (1994). The design of educational technology is the theoretical basis of practice in the world of learning in expanding education through academic performance. AECT (2004) There are four studies on research, the preparation of the code of ethics that is carried out, educational technology, and theory of research practice and sources of information in the learning process. From several approaches described above, various educational solutions and learning processes can improve performance through the process of technological resources.

Educational technology advancement in developing countries

Education and technology are elementary to adapt and move according to the demands of the times in developing countries, with other developing countries such as India experiencing very rapid development. By developing flexible systems in alternative curricula, multilevel classroom organizations with innovative activities, and continuous support systems such as teachers and lecturers or teaching staff, educational technology has experienced a relatively rapid development cycle.

Methods

The quality of technology-based education is based on the participatory principle of all parties involved. Planning together, carrying out activities, monitoring and evaluating together with the extent to which the progress of activities takes place. All engaged in advancing the world of education participate as facilitators accompanied by people with relevant scientific backgrounds and experience in teaching and IT experts and observers such as the government and simultaneously involve stakeholders. A technology-based method with the following steps;

The first stage, Need Assessment/mapping of the condition of the area, education and students in various places, can determine the next steps in a preventive manner that are

suitable to be implemented in the technology-based area. This mapping involves administrators from the government, stakeholders from lecturers, students, village officials and the community. The second stage is to determine the appropriate education technology scheme strategy by considering several regional conditions and situations and whether students in the area can catch internet signals or if internet access is sufficient.

Results

Education has influence, and the latest path technology to improve knowledge and ability to compete in the global era will be one of the country's benchmarks in implementing technology in education can be seen in the following sectors: a. Primary and Secondary Education, b—Higher Education, c. Distance Learning, d. Special Education, e. Education and Training, h. In Language Education, Education and technology are urgently needed to improve the efficiency and productivity of education management. In other words, delaying the application of information technology in educational institutions means waiting for the smooth running of education in the face of global competition. Strategic issues of ICT as a source of knowledge. It will be able to improve education through teaching aids (Learning Tools), ICT as ICT educational facilities, as ICT competency standards as administrative support for management education as an educational infrastructure. Media technology and educational literacy have developed on various platforms. The existence of data and information sources and a means of exchanging data and information is inevitable in this modern era, and communicating quickly without any boundaries of the territory, space or time, opening information sources that were previously difficult to access becomes very easy to expand. data becomes information to support decision making—ICT-based education management, including cataloguing.

The existence of data storage and processing and others from these impacts need to involve experts so that generations or people who are less sophisticated in using technology so that these impacts can be anticipated by the government and academics and ICT experts on the provision of information about developments of education do not misuse unlimited technology. Education and technology in the Primary and Secondary education sector, technology are expected to affect motivation, strengthen teaching, and improve the psychological environment in the Higher Education classroom. The use of technology is intended to stimulate and motivate students to develop their intellectual abilities to establish research and development knowledge, both theoretical and applied Distance Learning, providing an intermediary medium between students and their educational institutions.

Conclusion and Advice

Government policies are predicted to increase the development of information technology in various regions, especially prioritizing internet network access in areas that are still limited and constrained by the lack of access to information processing networks and not only focusing on places or big cities as is happening at this time. Because the area's role in supporting the development of information technology and the development of education in Indonesia is significant. The media have a tremendous influence on the development of the world of education and technology, showing the capabilities and traces of the legacy of a

society's expertise in future civilizations. Government involvement is needed to sponsor technology education schemes and classes to strengthen institutions in increasing research and promoting education through how to use the positive impact of technology policies.

References

- [1] Astuti, SantiIndra. 2004. *Building a Media Literacy Society* (Article in HU MindPeople.
- [2] Apridara, Khalsiah, Anwar Puteh , Rita Mutia, TeukuAzhari, 2020, “The Impact of Benefits and Risks of Social Media on Adolescents.” *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*. www.ijicc.net, Volume, 76-80, ISSN 2201-1323.
- [3] Berger, Arthur Asa. *Media Research Techniques* (2nd edition). London: SAGE Publications, 1998..
- [4] Chavanu, Bakari. “10 Classroom Approaches to Media Literacy.” Article in *The Media Literacy Resource Guide*. Ontario: Ontario Ministry of Education, 1989..
- [5] Khalsiah, et.al “Fiction and Nonfiction Novel: Characteristics Possessed To Allure The Reader.” *Talent Development & Excellence*, Vol.12, 2081-2088, ISSN 1869-0459 (print)/ ISSN 1869-2885 (online), 2020.
- [6] Noor Cahyanto, 2007 “Utilization of ICT in Building International Learning Networks.” *Indonesian Teachers' Conference*. Jakarta, November 2007.
- [7] Potter, James W. *Media Literacy*. New York: SAGE Publications, 2002.
- [8] RC Sharma. “Educational Technology global implementation Policy Review and Analysis.” *International Forum on Open and Distance Education Beijing*, 2009.
- [9] Yuyun Estriyanto, MT, “Utilization of Information Technology in Learning” Jakarta 15 February 2008.
- [10] Yuhadi, Marso. “Humanist technology in educational journals.” 2007.

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution4.0 International License.